

RESEARCH INNOVATION AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN LIBRARIES: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

This research paper explores the challenges faced by libraries in adapting to digital transformations and identifies strategies within the realm of Information and Library Science (ILS) to navigate these challenges successfully. Key challenges in digital transformation include resistance to cultural change, a lack of clear strategy and leadership, digital skill gaps, the complexity of integrating legacy systems, budget constraints, and significant data security and privacy risks. The logistics management business process of contractual support of a freight transportation service is being developed with options for business development from a basic freight transportation service to an integrated transport and logistics service of the 3PL level and the prospect of transition to a 4PL service. The lack of studies regarding the innovative impact to logistics management defines the research gap. Taking into account the strategic priorities of the target digital models of the transport and logistics business, the logistics management requires innovative solutions in business models regarding the issues of contractual support. The research question could be treated as investigating the innovative changes in business models driven by a smart contracting system in the company as a component of the business information architecture. The article examines the features of business processes in the age of digitalization taking into account the digital transformation of several key aspects of the theory of general economic and functional management. The practical significance of the study is due to the innovational aspects of the modern management procedures using the digitalization tools

Keywords :Digital innovation, research innovation and digital transformation in libraries, Digital transformation

1. Introduction :

Digital Transformation has become a defining aspect of the contemporary library landscape, reshaping the way information is accessed, stored, and disseminated. In this digital era, libraries are compelled to undergo significant changes to meet the evolving needs of users and to remain relevant in an increasingly technology-driven society. The digital transformation in libraries

refers to the integration of digital technologies to enhance traditional library functions and services. This shift encompasses a broad spectrum, ranging from the digitization of archival materials to the implementation of advanced technologies in library operations. Libraries are transitioning from physical repositories of books to dynamic, technology-driven hubs for information and knowledge. Libraries are leveraging digital technologies to expand their reach and democratize access to information. The adoption of digital platforms, online databases, and virtual services has become crucial for libraries seeking to bridge the gap between traditional and modern information landscapes. The shift towards a more digital-centric model is not just a matter of convenience but is essential for the survival and relevance of libraries in a society where information is increasingly consumed in digital formats.

2. Digital innovation as a means to study innovation generally:

While digital innovation can be distinguished by its characteristics, it also serves as a powerful context with which to study innovation more generally, particularly the meta-characteristics of innovation processes. The reality is that digitalisation cuts across the entire innovation value chain. Consequently, many aspects of digital innovation affect the theory and practice of innovation more generally. One aspect of digital innovation that lets us better study and understand general innovation processes is the speed with which it unfolds. For instance, the many iterative steps involved in an innovation process occur more rapidly in digital contexts. This phenomenon, which Malhotra and Majchrzak (2021) call the ‘fruit fly effect’, provides innovation scholars with evidence on many cycles of innovation that previously required years or decades to unfold. Furthermore, the ability to monitor parallel and multiple sequential innovation cycles means that research into digital innovation makes it possible for scholars to benefit from a fast-paced evolution of knowledge accumulation. Ideally, this implies that studying digital innovation can provide insights on complex processes such as the co-evolution of innovations in ecosystem contexts.

A second aspect of digital innovation is the observability of the innovation process due to the self-documenting nature of digital innovation (Garud et al., 2008). As noted by Malhotra and Majchrzak (2021), the interaction between participants in digital innovation occurs through digital knowledge artefacts. Essentially, this means that when digital innovation occurs, data is created at all stages of the innovation process, leaving digital traces (Garud et al., 2011; Pentland et al., 2020). This characteristic facilitates collaboration in digital innovation: as participants come and go, they can read what others have contributed and then add their contributions. This feature of digital innovation has direct implications for innovation research as the collection of data of innovation processes was difficult for many studies in the pre-digital age. However, with digital innovation, we are able to naturally document much more of the phenomenon. Digital innovation provides a wealth of data not only of the characteristics of the digital innovation outcomes, but also of the processes and micro-level interactions that lead to their creation and dissemination.

A third aspect of studying digital innovation emerges as a product of the first two: the relationships between the multiple levels of analysis (such as the micro, organizational and macro) can be more easily traced due to the speed, scale, and observability of the digital innovation process. This stands in stark contrast to traditional and non-digital settings where it is more challenging to study innovation across multiple levels. In sum, the availability of digital traces of interactions allows the study of the processes of innovation in unprecedented ways.

Because of these advantages in studying digital innovation, using digital innovation as a ‘model of’ also provides a ‘model for’ the study of innovation processes more broadly in non digital, and hybrid contexts. For instance, the investigation of Gonzalez and Gulbrandsen (2021) into the Norwegian newspaper industry illustrates how an established industry with a resilient identity can learn how to use the digital space to adapt and innovate effectively. They find that continuous experimentation and collective deliberation on the fit between innovation and the dominant identity is a key process of innovation adoption more generally. Similarly, Garud and Karunakaran (2018) document how participative experimentation at Google using digital tools led to the emergence of Gmail and AdSense, arguably two of the main digital innovations among many at Google that led to its transformation over time. Relatedly, Leonardi et al. (2021) show how digital simulation models can be leveraged to explain and predict complex systems. As complex tools, however, these models must become integrated into a social context characterised by differences in technical knowledge about when, how, and why the models are useful. They compare three very different contexts and show that building in digital innovations requires appeals to the credibility of the model’s analysis, the utility of its outputs, and to negotiate unavoidable political issues that emerge from differing values among parties in the innovation process. These papers show that the abundance of digital trace data allows not only scholars to learn, but also allows practitioners to better understand complex processes, allowing complex technical and socio-technical system to be simulated (cf. Parmar et al., 2020)

3. Digital Transformation Strategies: The digital transformation framework describes the cornerstones of the transformation along four dimensions. Future research should seek to further identify and concretize common elements that can be attributed to these four dimensions. This pertains in particular to the different attributes companies could adopt for each of these elements. Empirical insights could help comparing digital transformation strategies across different industries to assess commonalities as well as differences, in order to increase success rates. One key question relates to the optimal extent of digitization that a firm should achieve, since greater use of digital technologies may not always be desirable (Grover and Kohli 2013). Future research should analyze whether a firm’s size or the extent to which its core products can be digitized have different influences in this respect. Likewise, it is of great interest whether successful patterns for B2C companies differ from those of B2B companies. digital transformations are often accompanied by changing skill sets that are not only necessary for the transformation itself, but also for regular operations thereafter. While current staff members may have a different, less tech-savvy mindset and may lack the required technological capabilities to

cope with the upcoming changes, new highly skilled and focused staff members might be difficult to find, given the particular location of a firm. Research could support firms by providing guidance on the assessment of their existing technological capabilities and on procedures to weigh up their current options, as well as guidance on the design of training procedures for current employees and new hires.

4. Integrating Digital Transformation Strategies into Firms:

As noted, digital transformation strategies have a cross-functional character and need to be aligned with other functional and operational strategies. However, the alignment of IT strategies with other strategies has remained a difficult and controversial endeavor. Given the rather recent appearance of digital transformation strategies, further evidence is needed as to how this alignment can be conducted in practice – not only related to IT strategies, but also from an organizational perspective. In this respect, the interaction of digital transformation strategies with business development and business models also needs to be assessed from a management perspective. Since digital transformation strategies cut across various other strategies at the same time, complex coordination efforts might be needed. Research should provide guidelines for firms to help structure these processes in order to achieve shared goal-setting, the alignment of different strategies, and cooperation between various people and entities throughout a firm.

5. Organizing Digital Innovation: From Processes to Practices

How can an organization advance its digital innovation capabilities? Traditionally, innovation has often been described as a discrete, linear, and sequential innovation process with clearly ordered, differentiated, and consecutive phases. For instance, Tidd and Bessant (2011) divide the innovation process into search, select, implement, and capture. Chesbrough (2003) differentiates between research and development. Desouza's (2011) innovation process consists of idea generation, advocacy & screening, experimentation, commercialization, and diffusion & implementation. And Fichman et al. (2014) distinguish between discovery, development, diffusion, and impact. The purpose of such innovation processes is essentially to coordinate the activities of individual agents and to organize these activities reasonably well according to given, recurring circumstances (Tidd and Bessant 2011). Such innovation processes are also necessary conditions for digital innovations, but they alone are not sufficient for advancing the digital innovation capabilities of an organization: Digital innovation capabilities are enhanced if organizations support combinatorial and distributed innovations. For this goal, companies also need to understand and support the "practices" (cf. Tuomi 2002) of those who actively develop digital innovations. In the context of digital innovation, we refer to this as "Digital Innovation Practices".

6. Challenges in Digital Transformation

The digital transformation of libraries introduces a spectrum of challenges that demand strategic solutions. These challenges encompass various facets of library operations, and a thorough

examination is crucial to formulate effective strategies. Here, we delve into key challenges faced by libraries in their journey toward digital transformation.

1. Technological Obsolescence

Managing and updating technology infrastructure to keep pace with rapid advancements. Balancing the integration of emerging technologies with budgetary constraints.

2. Information Accessibility

Ensuring equitable access to digital resources for diverse user groups. Addressing the digital divide to promote inclusivity in information access

7. Organizational & Strategic Challenges :

Resistance to Change: A major hurdle is the ingrained mindset of employees and leadership, which can be comfortable with existing processes and fear job security or the unknown.

1. **Lack of Clear Strategy:** Without a well-defined digital roadmap, efforts can become fragmented, resource-intensive, and fail to meet organizational goals.
2. **Leadership Alignment:** Misaligned leadership and insufficient sponsorship can lead to a lack of unified vision and slow down the transformation process.
3. **Siloed Organizational Structures:** Disparate business units operating in isolation hinder cross-functional alignment and can create disconnected initiatives.
4. **Inadequate Change Management:** A lack of a thorough change management strategy can lead to confusion, resistance, and failed transformation efforts.
5. **Technical & Infrastructure Challenges :**
6. **Legacy Systems:** Integrating complex, outdated legacy systems with new digital technologies presents significant technical and data integration challenges.
7. **Data Management & Security:** Managing large volumes of digital data while maintaining privacy and robust cybersecurity measures to combat growing cybercrime is a significant concern.
8. **Complex Software & Technology:** New technologies can be intimidating, leading to implementation difficulties and negative end-user experiences.
9. **Resource & Skill Challenges:**
10. **Skill Gaps:** The rapid advancement of digital tools requires employees to have new digital literacy and skills, which may be lacking within the existing workforce.
11. **Budget Constraints:** Digital transformation requires significant financial investment, and insufficient budgets can prevent organizations from acquiring the necessary resources and talent.
12. **Customer-Facing Challenges**
13. **Evolving Customer Expectations:** Customers expect seamless, fast, and personalized digital experiences across all channels, which can be difficult to deliver consistently.

14. Omni-Channel Integration: Providing a uniform experience across various online and offline touch points requires integrating communication and service channels effectively.

8. Conclusion:

While this introductory essay provides a background for and an overview of this special issue on digital innovation, it also begins sketching out the frontier of our knowledge on the topic. As an emerging phenomenon, digital innovation is likely to have a significant impact on innovation research in general, offering great opportunities for research while creating new challenges as well. While researchers have established some attributes of digital innovation, others have yet to be charted. Researching these attributes can offer greater insight into digital transformation processes and the dis-ruptions involved. Libraries of the 21st century have responded to the demands of the moment. The quest for digital content among the public is high and library users are no exception. This has put libraries on their feet because they need to respond proactively to attract and sustain the attention of the users. This is important because library users of the digital media age have many media contents competing for their attention. Most of these media are packed in contents format that endear them to the users. This reality even makes the job of libraries more challenging because the competition is stiffer that they may imagine. This study recommend that libraries should continue to present contents in formats that could attract the attention of library users. It is also suggested that library management should monitor trends in the digital transformation closely and make adjustments where there is need.

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